

PERIOPSIS

Climate-smart Forestry (CSF)

Building Resilience for Mediterranean Forests

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Training Overview

Module 1: Introduction to CSF and successful case studies

- Introduction to CSF
- Principles of CSF
- Forests as Carbon Sinks

Module 3: Climate change: Threats and Challenges to Mediterranean forests

- Anthropogenic Threats
- Biotic and Abiotic Hazards
- Vulnerability of Forests in Cyprus

Module 2: Mediterranean forests and their significance

- Mediterranean Forests' Characteristics
- Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services
- Socioeconomic Importance of Mediterranean Forests

Module 4: CSF Application to Mediterranean forests

1. Implementing CSF Practices
2. Restoration Strategies Using Emerging Technologies
3. Stakeholder Engagement in CSF Decision-Making

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3. Climate Change: Threats and Challenges to Mediterranean Forests

Anthropogenic Threats

A significant source of the deterioration, destruction and loss for ecosystems (habitats and species) and with a potential to magnify or trigger many environmental threats:

- **Unsustainable Logging**
 - Most logging activities, either legal or illegal, do not employ reduced impact logging (RIL) practices, contributing to unnecessary forest damage. (from WWF video – not or mediterranean forests specifically)
Degraded forests become more vulnerable to pests, diseases, and fire.
- **Overgrazing, land use change, urban expansion, and land abandonment**
 - These practices reduce forest cover, fragment habitats, and degrade soils. Land abandonment often leads to fuel accumulation, increasing the severity of wildfires.

3. Climate Change: Threats and Challenges to Mediterranean Forests

Anthropogenic Threats

- **Rising Demand for Wood**

- By 2050, demand for wood products (particularly for bioenergy feedstock) is expected to triple compared to 2010 levels. Sustainable logging practices are needed to meet this demand, to counter increased deforestation and emissions.

- **Weak Governance**

- Weak governance can exacerbate illegal logging and forest degradation.

- **Water Scarcity & Soil Degradation**

- Intensive agriculture, over-extraction of water, and poor land management deplete water resources. Soil erosion and further undermine forest productivity and resilience.

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Abiotic Hazards

Abiotic hazards are non-living factors that can severely impact forest ecosystems. While they may be partially natural, climate change and human activities often exacerbate their frequency or intensity.

- **Forest fires:**
 - Forest fires are becoming more severe due to fuel accumulation and higher flammability from land abandonment, rising temperatures, drought, and other risks and hazards. Forest fires are amongst the most impactful hazards of forests and in some cases result in the loss of human life.

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Abiotic Hazards

- **Extreme Drought and Heat Events:**
 - Rise in temperatures and increase in seasonality (even daily accumulation) of rainfall lead to increase in floods and prolonged droughts, putting Mediterranean forests under severe stress. Increased frequency and severity of droughts and heatwaves are major contributors to forest decline and tree mortality.
 - Without precautionary measures, drought-related tree decay and forest fires are likely to increase, further exacerbating forest decline. Water scarcity is a critical growth constraint for Mediterranean trees, with projections showing intensified drought conditions.

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Abiotic Hazards

- **Storms and Windthrow:**
 - Strong winds can uproot or damage trees, particularly in densely planted or poorly managed stands. Windstorms can also escalate pest outbreaks when damaged trees become more susceptible to insects and diseases.
- **Erosion:**
 - When forest cover is lost or degraded, soil stability declines, accelerating soil erosion.
 - Hazard especially evident on steep slopes (alpine, subalpine areas).

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Biotic Hazards

Biotic Hazards arise from **living organisms** that threaten forest health. They are expected to intensify, compounding stress on forests and altering ecosystem dynamics.

- **Insects:**
 - Bark beetle outbreaks, for example, can decimate large areas of stressed or monoculture forests. Warmer temperatures can expand insect ranges and increase reproduction rates.
- **Diseases and pathogens:**
 - Fungi, bacteria, and viruses may proliferate under changing climate conditions. Weakened trees (due to drought or other stressors) are more susceptible to infections.

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The Cross-Cutting Role of Climate Change

While anthropogenic activities directly cause deforestation and overexploitation, climate change compounds both abiotic and biotic threats:

- **Higher Temperatures and Altered Rainfall:** Intensify drought, heatwaves, and wildfire conditions.
- **Shifting Pest and Disease Patterns:** Warmer climates and stressed forests create ideal conditions for pests/diseases to spread.
- **Ecosystem Imbalance:** Forests already under stress from human activities have reduced resilience to withstand extreme weather events.

Proactive forest management is critical to addressing these challenges, ensuring long-term productivity and minimizing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions.

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Vulnerability of Forests in Cyprus

Forest Characteristics in Cyprus

- Cyprus is renowned for its natural forests with **rich biodiversity** and **unique flora**, boasting a variety of tree types, each with **distinct ecological characteristics and significance**.
- Cyprus forests comprise **18.7% of land area**
- The forest area has remained stable since 2000.
- Cyprus forests comprise **18.7% of land area**
- Above-ground biomass and growing stock have increased significantly since 1990.

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Vulnerability of Forests in Cyprus

Forest Composition

- Dominated by *Pinus brutia* (Calabrian or Turkish pine) in lower to mid elevations, *Quercus alnifolia* (golden oak), cypress, and cedar species (mainly *Cedrus brevifolia*) in higher elevations.
- Some endemic species add to the island's unique biodiversity (e.g., *Cedrus brevifolia* in the Troodos range).

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Vulnerability of Forests in Cyprus

Policy and Management:

- **Forest Law** enacted in 2012 and **forest policy statement** in 2013.
- **Forest Management Plans are mandatory** and registered with an official body, but **no National Forest Programme exists**.
- **No forests certified** under third-party schemes.

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Vulnerability of Forests in Cyprus

Disturbances and Protections:

- In 2010, 1.4% of forests were reported as damaged by insects, diseases, and fires.
- Approx. 6.8% of forests and other woodlands are protected for biodiversity;
- 13 thousand ha are considered undisturbed by human activity.

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Vulnerability of Forests in Cyprus

Economic Contribution:

- Minimal contribution to the country's GDP.
- Very low levels of marketed roundwood.
- Most wood removals are used as fuel
- Forest sector employs approx. 4,000 people.

Key Vulnerabilities:

- High risk due to water scarcity, prolonged droughts, frequent heatwaves, soil degradation, and urban expansion.
- Limited adaptive capacity without intervention.
- Fragmented habitats and small forest areas intensify challenges.

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Vulnerability of Forests in Cyprus

Future projections:

- Reduction of forest capital in the Mediterranean.
- Higher fire risks and biodiversity loss.

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The Need for Sustainable Management

Strategies for Adaptation:

- **Fire-Smart Landscapes:** Design landscapes to manage/reduce wildfire risk, including the use of thinning and controlled burns.
- **Drought-Resilient Species:** Encourage planting species better suited to future climatic conditions.
- **Integrated Pest Management:** Maintain biodiversity and biological controls to address pest outbreaks.

Adaptive Management Frameworks:

- Develop/adopt indicators to assess resilience and recovery to disturbances.
- Link observational approaches with experimental to refine forest management strategies.

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The Need for Sustainable Management

Participation in International Fora and Agreements, with specific targets, obligations and indicators

Cyprus participates in global agreements including:

- The Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD).
- The United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC).
- The United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification (UNCCD).
- The Kyoto Protocol and Paris Agreement.

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Case Study: Invasive Species in Cyprus

Examples of invasive species in Cyprus:

- **Callosciurus finlaysonii (Finlayson's Squirrel)**
 - Varies in color (white/red/black morphs). Opportunistic feeder; can prey on bird eggs.
 - Native to Southeast Asia; introduced in Italy, could potentially establish in Cyprus.
 - **Management:** Prevent release of captive animals, early detection & rapid response.

Source: European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment. (2023). *An introduction to the invasive alien species of Union concern: version 2022*. Publications Office of the European Union.

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Case Study: Invasive Species in Cyprus

Examples of invasive species in Cyprus:

- **Solenopsis geminata (Tropical Fire Ant)**
 - Small, orange-brown body. Forms large supercolonies.
 - Recorded in Cyprus, Greece, Italy, Netherlands—no established population in Cyprus yet.
 - **Impacts:** Disrupts seed dispersal, poses human health risks, damages crops.
 - **Management:** Treat soils/plants before transport; multi-year strategies to eradicate nests.

Source: European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment. (2023). *An introduction to the invasive alien species of Union concern: version 2022*. Publications Office of the European Union.

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Case Study: Invasive Species in Cyprus

Examples of invasive species in Cyprus:

- **Acacia saligna (Golden Wreath Wattle)**
 - Evergreen shrub/tree; quickly spreads after fire/disturbance.
 - Established in Spain, Cyprus, Italy, Portugal. Outcompetes native flora, alters fire regimes.
 - **Management:** Integrated mechanical, chemical, and sometimes biological control.

Source: European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment. (2023). *An introduction to the invasive alien species of Union concern: version 2022*. Publications Office of the European Union.

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Case Study: Invasive Species in Cyprus

Examples of invasive species in Cyprus:

- **Ailanthus altissima (Tree of Heaven)**
 - Fast-growing deciduous tree with allelopathic effects.
 - Present in 18 EU Member States, including Cyprus. Forms dense stands, displacing natives.
 - **Management:** Prevent planting, remove seedlings promptly, combine mechanical + chemical control.

Source: European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment. (2023). *An introduction to the invasive alien species of Union concern: version 2022*. Publications Office of the European Union.

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Case Study: Invasive Species in Cyprus

Examples of invasive species in Cyprus:

- **Prosopis juliflora (Mesquite)**
 - Thorny shrub/small tree with deep roots. Forms dense thickets in disturbed areas.
 - Established in Spain; threatens frost-free regions.
 - **Management:** Early removal, integrated treatments, cross-border coordination.

Source: European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment. (2023). *An introduction to the invasive alien species of Union concern: version 2022*. Publications Office of the European Union.

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